

Tetradecyltrimethylammonium permanganate : a novel potassium permanganate derived reagent for *trans*-dichlorination, *trans*-dibromination and *cis*-dihydroxylation of olefins[†]

Braja G. Hazra* and Vandana S. Pore

Division of Organic Chemistry Synthesis, National Chemical Laboratory, Pune-411 008, India

E-mail : hazra@ems.ncl.res.in; vspore@dalton.ncl.res.in

Fax : 91-20-25893153; 91-20-25893355

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Reactivity of KMnO_4 has been modified by converting it into long chain quaternary ammonium permanganate salt, viz., tetradecyltrimethylammonium permanganate (TDTAP). This new versatile, stable reagent has been utilised for chemoselective and stereoselective *trans*-dichlorination and dibromination of a variety of alkenes. Use of this reagent for vicinal dihydroxylation of alkenes in a two phase solvent system has also been demonstrated. The mechanism for the *trans*-dichlorination reaction and the nature of the reacting species has been proposed.

Potassium permanganate exhibits unique reactivity towards olefins. However its utility in organic synthesis has been severely limited by solubility problems. In an attempt to improve and modify the reactivity of potassium permanganate, several quaternary ammonium permanganates have been prepared, characterised and used. Solubility studies indicate that these compounds exist in solution as either ion pair or aggregates, with aggregation being promoted by high concentration, low temperature and solvents of low polarity. Detonation of quaternary ammonium permanganates during drying at elevated temperatures have been reported^{1,2}. A systematic study has shown that salts containing unsaturated groups in the cation ($\text{PhCH}_2\text{N}^+\text{Et}_3$, $\text{PhCH}_2\text{N}^+\text{Me}_3$, $\text{Ph}_3\text{N}^+\text{Me}$, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}^+\text{Me}$) decomposed with explosive violence when the temperature is reached 80–90°. Compounds with a saturated alkyl chain (Et_4N^+ , Bu_4N^+ , $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{15}\text{N}^+\text{Me}_3$), on the other hand, showed no explosive tendency, but they did decompose passively between 80° and 100°.

We have recently prepared tetradecyltrimethylammonium permanganate (TDTAP) salt and demonstrated its use as an excellent reagent for the chemoselective and stereoselective *trans*-dichlorination³ and dibromination⁴ of a variety of alkenes. Vicinal dihydroxylation⁵ of alkenes with TDTAP and potassium hydroxide in a two phase solvent system has also been reported by us.

TDTAP, a violet crystalline solid, stable at room temperature for a few days, can be stored at 0° in a brown bottle for months and is highly soluble in methylene dichloride.

This new reagent is readily prepared as follows :

To a stirred solution of potassium permanganate (7.9 g, 50 mmol) in water (250 ml) at 25° was added dropwise over 30 min a solution of tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromide (17.5 g, 52 mmol) in water (250 ml) when a violet coloured precipitate formed immediately. The mixture was stirred for further 30 min the violet precipitate was filtered off, washed thoroughly with water and dried in vacuo over P_2O_5 to furnish TDTAP (17.25 g, 92%), m.p. 165–170°.

The main disadvantage of the related reagent benzyltrimethylammonium permanganate is its instability^{1,2}, arises because of the easily formed benzyl radical initiates a chain reaction during drying or when this reagent is handled neat. In view of this it was expected that replacement of benzyl group by a long chain hydrocarbon radical, e.g. tetradecyl, would give rise to increased stability and solubility.

Differential thermal analysis of TDTAP has shown its decomposition to be stepwise exothermic process which starts at 102.3°, with the thermogram reaching a maxima at 119.5°. This clearly indicates that TDTAP decomposes passively at a relative higher temperature compared with earlier reported quaternary permanganate salts. In fact, as mentioned earlier, this salt being stable for months at 0° permits its ready access, whenever required.

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

Manganese-mediated stereoselective and chemoselective *trans*-dichlorination of alkenes with tetradecyltrimethylammonium permanganate-trimethylchlorosilane

Formation of *vic*-dichlorides by addition of molecular chlorine to olefins has limited synthetic utility due to the occurrence of side reactions⁶. Moreover use of gaseous chlorine presents a potential environmental hazard and its quantitative utilization is hard to work out. Several other reagents add chlorine to double bonds. Sulfuryl chloride⁷ reacts readily with most of the ethylenic compounds to yield saturated dichloro derivatives with evolution of sulfur dioxide. Reaction of trichloroamine⁸ with olefins provides a simple means for the preparation of *vic*-dichlorides. Phosphorous pentachloride⁹, antimony pentachloride¹⁰, iodobenzene dichloride¹¹, tetrabutylammonium iodotetra-chloride¹² and copper(II) chloride¹³ have been examined as chlorinating agents with good results in certain cases. *cis*-Vicinal dichlorinations of olefins by molybdenum(VI)-acetyl chloride¹⁴ and manganese(III) acetate-calcium chloride¹⁵ have been reported. *trans*-Vicinal dichlorination of olefins with manganese dioxide-trimethylchlorosilane (TMCS)¹⁶ and MnO₂-MnCl₂-acetyl chloride¹⁷ and acetal chlorination with MnO₂-TMCS¹⁸ have been documented. However, non-homogeneity of these inorganic based reagents in commonly used organic solvents limits their wider synthetic applications. In order to overcome this difficulty Marco *et al.* used^{19,20} benzyltriethylammonium permanganate and oxalyl chloride in methylene dichloride. Recently these authors also reported²¹ the use of KMnO₄-trimethyl-chlorosilane in the presence of benzyltriethylammonium chloride to dichlorinate alkenes, open the epoxides and chemoselectively oxidize sulfides to sulfoxides. *vic*-Dichlorination with hexachloroethane²² in the presence of RuCl₂(PPh₃)₃ as a catalyst and sodium chlorite²³ in the presence of Mn(acac)₃ and moist alumina have also been reported. As mentioned above there are severe drawbacks in terms of safety due to decomposition of the reagent when reagent-containing benzyl radical is used. We have reported³ the use of TDTAP in combination with trimethylchlorosilane (TMCS) to lead chemoselective and stereoselective *trans*-dichlorination of alkenes (Table 1).

This TDTAP-TMCS reagent displays high chemoselectivity as evident from the inert nature of the conjugated double bond of 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate (16-DPA) **3**, the electron-deficient double bond of carvone **5**, or with benzylic as well as the electron deficient double bond of coumarin **8**. In the stigmasterol derivative 2,22-dien-6-one **2** the 22-*E*-double bond is sterically hindered by the (24*S*)-

Table 1. *trans*-Dichlorination of alkenes with TDTAP-TMCS

Starting compound	Product	Yield (%)
	96	
	88	
	87	
	92	
	62	
	84	
	90	
	No Reaction	

ethyl and D ring of the steroid, thus hindering the approach of the chlorinating species. The only product isolated in this case is 2,3-diaxial dichloride **10**.

The reaction of 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate **3** and carvone **5** in methylene dichloride with excess of chlorine gas at 0 to 3° for 1.5 h furnished a complex reaction mixture of polychlorinated products. Addition of chlorine to both double bonds took place in both the cases. Column chromatographic purification of polychlorinated products afforded 3β-acetoxy-5,6,16,17-tetrachloro-5α-pregnan-20-one, 3β-acetoxy-5,6,16,17,21-pentachloro-5α-pregnan-20-one from 16-DPA **3** and two more unidentified compounds. The desired 5,6-dichlorinated product **11** could not be isolated from this reaction. In case of carvone **5** also hepta and nona chlorinated products were isolated by column chromatography. No trace of the desired 9,10-dichlorocarvone **13** was found in this chlorination reaction. On the other

peroxide and benzyltrimethylammonium chloride in carbon tetrachloride have been used²⁸ to brominate alkenes. TDTAP in combination with trimethylbromosilane (TMBS) provides⁴ a simple and mild method for stereoselective and chemoselective *trans*-dibromination of alkenes (Table 2).

Starting compound	Product	Yield (%)
	91	
	85	
	89	
	79	
	73	
	62	
	60	
	60	

A violet-coloured solution of TDTAP in methylene dichloride at 0 to 3° changed immediately to deep brown on treatment with TMBS. The olefin in methylene dichloride was added to this mixture which was then stirred at 0 to 3° for 1.5 h.

This TDTAP-TMBS reagent displays high chemoselectivity as evidenced by no reaction of α,β -unsaturated double bond at C-16 of 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate **3**, the electron-deficient double bond of carvone **5** and nona-3,8-dien-2-one **17**. In the stigmaterol derivative 2,22-dien-6-one **2** the 22-*E*-double bond is sterically hindered by the (24*S*)-ethyl and D ring of the steroid, thus hindering the approach of the brominating species. The only product isolated in this

case is 2,3-diaxial dibromide **19**.

The probable pathway for the *trans*-vicinal dibromination of alkenes with TDTAP-TMBS can be represented as follows (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

The reaction of 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate **3** in methylene dichloride at 0 to 3° with 1 mol equiv. of bromine in methylene dichloride was instantaneous. The product isolated after 3 min was 5 α ,6 β ,16 β ,17 α -tetrabromide (21%), starting pregnenolone acetate (76%) with no trace of 5 α ,6 β -dibromide **20**. The stigmaterol derivative 2,22-dien-6-one **2** on reaction with 1 mol equiv. of bromine in methylene dichloride at 0 to 3° for 5 min furnished a complex mixture of products from which a small amount of 2 β ,3 α ,22,23-tetrabromide (6%) was isolated. With two mol equiv. of bromine at 0 to 3° for 1.5 h, a similar complex mixture formed containing small amount of same tetrabromide. With TDTAP-TMBS formation of dibrominated compound **19** as a single product in very good yield strongly suggests that *trans*-dibromination occurs by a different pathway and clearly rules out the possibility of generation of molecular bromine in the reaction medium as the brominating species.

Vicinal dihydroxylation of alkenes with tetradecyltrimethylammonium permanganate and potassium hydroxide in a two-phase solvent system

Potassium permanganate is a very strong oxidizing agent. It has been established beyond doubt that the low-temperature oxidation of alkenes with aqueous alkaline potassium permanganate yields mainly 1,2-glycols, by *cis*-hydroxylation. The cyclic manganese(V) ester intermediate is unstable, and is rapidly hydrolysed at both C-O-Mn bonds, more or less simultaneously to yield diols²⁹⁻³¹. The yields of diols, however are seldom above 50% though they can be improved with phase transfer catalysis³²⁻³⁴ or increased

stirring³⁵. Preparation and absorption spectrum of a stable solution of manganese(V) diester by reacting alkenes with pulverised potassium permanganate in dichloromethane and benzyltriethylammonium chloride as a phase transfer agent has been reported^{36,37} by Ogino and his group. It is probable that the intermediate manganate(V) diester could be more stable under these conditions because it would be complexed with the quaternary ammonium ion and the hydrolysis reaction would be suppressed in the absence of water. This procedure³⁶ provided a simple route to a number of diols from alkenes in good yields. The first example of the use of stable cetyltrimethylammonium permanganate salt for the *cis*-dihydroxylation of alkenes has been published³⁸ by Chandrasekaran and co-workers.

As an extension of Chandrasekaran's and to some extent Ogino's work, we have reported⁵ the first practical and acceptable yields of vicinal *cis*-diols from alkenes with tetradecyltrimethylammonium permanganate (TDTAP) salt and addition of potassium hydroxide at the beginning in *tert*-BuOH-CH₂Cl₂-H₂O as the solvent system.

Treatment of alkene (1 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ with solution of TDTAP (1.2 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ for 2 h at 30° followed by anhydrous or alkaline work-up³⁸ (Method A), the yields of diol from the alkenes we used are poor to moderate (Table 3). Carrying out the reaction in aqueous *tert*-butanol followed by treatment with alkali even lowers the yield of the diols. Continuing the reaction for a longer period does not improve the yield of diols. In all the cases varying amounts of starting materials recovered unchanged.

We found that when the reaction was conducted in a two phase solvent system of *tert*-butanol, CH₂Cl₂ and water in the ratio 50 : 10 : 1.25 in the presence of 0.1 mmol of KOH (Method C), dihydroxylation occurs in good yield. In the beginning, the pH of the reaction mixture is 7.5, which changes to 9.5 after the addition of aqueous KOH and remains the same throughout the entire reaction. The beneficial effect of addition of alkali at the beginning on the yields of diols in KMnO₄ oxidation of olefins is well known^{39,40}. A delicate balance for the formation of intermediate cyclic manganese(V) ester, its life time and its instant hydrolysis in alkaline condition (present from the beginning) in a two phase solvent system account for the increased diol formation.

Using bezyltrimethylammonium hydroxide as a base at the beginning in non aqueous solvent system of *tert*-butanol and CH₂Cl₂ (Method B), reasonably good yields of the diols are realised (Entry 1–4 in Table 3). Here again the delicate balance of the formation of cyclic ester and its hydrolysis with base soluble in the organic medium⁴¹ are respon-

Table 3. Dihydroxylation of alkenes with TDTAP

Starting compound	Product	Method	Yield (%)
	A	21	
		B	51
		C	73
	A	29	
		B	56
		C	76
	A	21	
		C	50
	A	45	
		C	69
	A	27	
		B	47
		C	71
	A	44	
		B	83
		C	78
	A	32	
		C	75
	A	39	
		C	56
	A	44	
		C	62

sible for the formation of the diols in respectable yields.

TDTAP is a reagent derived from potassium permanganate. It is very much expected that this reagent will add two -OH groups to a double bond like alkaline KMnO₄ or OsO₄ to give *cis*-diol from the less hindered side of the double bond. The *exo, cis*-diol **35** is the product of selective oxidation of *endo*-dicyclopentadiene **26** (Table 3). It is known^{42,43} that the nonbornane double bond of dicyclopentadiene **26** is the more reactive of the two. Again, the dihydroxylation of 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate **3**, takes place on the electron deficient α, β -unsaturated ketone to afford 3 β -acetoxy-16 $\alpha, 17\alpha$ -dihydroxypregna-5-en-20-one **32**. Potassium permanganate hydroxylation⁴⁴ and continuous permanganate oxidation⁴⁵ of 16-DPA, introduced the two *cis*-OH group at 16, 17 position from the less hindered side of the double

bond to give same compound **32**, leaving the 5,6-double bond unaffected.

cis-Diols were obtained in high yields from the corresponding alkenes using TDTAP, in a biphasic solvent system with inorganic base, or a homogenous system with organic base present from the beginning of the reaction.

General procedure : Method A : To a stirred solution of TDTAP (0.420 g, 1.12 mmol) in dichloromethane (10 ml) a solution of cholest-2-en-6-one **1** (0.384 g, 1 mmol) in dichloromethane (12 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at 30°. It was then treated with 5% aqueous NaOH (5 ml), stirred for 30 minutes. Usual work up followed by column chromatography over silica gel afforded pure cholest-2 α ,3 α -diol-6-one **30** (0.088 g, 21%) and starting material (0.204 g, 69%) was recovered back. (Carrying out the reaction in aqueous *tert*-butanol followed by treatment with alkali gave even lower yield).

Method B : A solution of cholest-2-ene-6-one **1** (0.384 g, 1 mmol) in *tert*-BuOH (8 ml) and CH₂Cl₂ (4 ml) was added to benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide (0.334 g, 2 mmol). To this magnetically stirred mixture, TDTAP (0.420 g, 1.12 mmol) was added in small portions during 2 min at 30°. The reaction mixture was stirred at this temperature for 1 h and then quenched with saturated aqueous solution of sodium bisulphite solution (10 ml). Usual work up followed by column chromatography over silica gel afforded pure cholest-2 α ,3 α -diol-6-one **30** (0.213 g, 51%) and starting (0.047 g, 16%) was recovered back.

Method C : To a magnetically stirred solution of cholest-2-ene-6-one **1** (0.384 g, 1 mmol) in *tert*-BuOH (10 ml) and CH₂Cl₂ (2 ml) at 30° was added a solution of KOH (0.006 g, 0.1 mmol) in water (0.5 ml) followed by TDTAP (0.420 g, 1.12 mmol) in small portions during five min. The reaction mixture was stirred at this temperature for 1 h and then quenched with saturated aqueous solution of sodium bisulphite solution (10 ml). Usual work up followed by column chromatography over silica gel afforded pure cholest-2 α ,3 α -diol-6-one **30** (0.305 g, 73%).

Conclusion : Reactivity of KMnO₄ has been modified by converting it into long chain quaternary ammonium salt, tetradecyltrimethylammonium permanganate. This novel reagent has been utilised for chemoselective and stereoselective *trans*-dichlorination, dibromination and vicinal dihydroxylation of a variety of alkenes. The UV-visible spectrum, EPR studies and stability pattern of the reacting brown species with that of MnOCl₃ lead us to propose the formation of MnOCl₃ in the reaction medium, which inserts two chlorine atoms in a stepwise manner to the alkene. Formation of molecular chlorine in the reaction medium has been

completely ruled out.

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